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Hydrologic processes analysis in a high Alpine catchment: the case of the Vallon de Nant

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By

Anthony Michelin

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JURY

Prof. Bettina Schaefli	Thesis director
Prof. Torsten Vennemann	Thesis co-director
Prof. Grégoire Mariéthoz	Internal expert
Dr. Ilja Van Meerveld	External expert
Prof. Marie-Elodie Perga	Jury president

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3 | Hydrological data

Photograph: the gauging station at the outlet of the Vallon de Nant in winter, with a partially frozen stream.

The overall work of this thesis relies on streamflow and meteorological characterization that will be respectively presented in this chapter and the following one. The study period started in 2016 at the same time as the commissioning of the gauging station at the outlet of the Vallon de Nant and benefited from its measures, but in return without historical records. The first part of this chapter presents the stream network (Section 3.1) and discusses in detail the streamflow measures at the outlet (Section 3.2) and their quality (Sections 3.3 and 3.4).

Some additional data sets acquired for this thesis work are excluded from this chapter and will be analyzed and discussed extensively in the Chapter 6 which presents the core of the hydrological process analysis; these data include soil temperature, water temperature, water conductivity and stable water isotopes.

3.1 Streamflow along the stream network

The Avançon de Nant is the main river that drains the Vallon de Nant up to its outlet at 1,200 m. asl. The Avançon de Nant length reaches 6 km in early summer (up to the Glacier des Martinets outlet), while during autumn and winter low flow, the main stream may start to flow as low as 1480 m asl., reducing the in-stream flow distance to the outlet to 2.95 km. The extent of the stream network (Figure 5) is based on observations during summer 2017 (dry and wet periods), and its exact path is calculated using MatLab based on the Swiss digital elevation model at a resolution of 2 m (swissAlti3D, 2012b) and the topo toolbox (Schwanghart and Scherler, 2014).

The river velocity in the main stream has been evaluated once using dye tracing (Figure 6). A fluorometer Albillia GGUN-FL30 (Albillia Sàrl, Neuchâtel, Switzerland) was set at the outlet while 5 g of rhodamine B and 5 g of fluorescein were injected in the main stream at 2.75 and 1.85 km upstream. Using the peak concentration as reference, the mean velocity of the stream between the two injection points was $0.28 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, accelerating to $0.59 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ over the last 1.85 km ($0.29 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ and $0.48 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ based on rising times).

Three along stream discharge estimations have been realized by salt dilution measurements by the Stream Biofilm and Ecosystem Research Laboratory group (EPFL) and the Catchment hydrology group (UNIL) from early August to early September in 2016 and 2017 by salt streamflow measurement (see Figure 7). Here are few remarks about these measures:

- Beyond 4.15 km upstream the outlet, the path taken for measurements diverges (streams *a* and *b* on the map Figure 5).

- On 9 August 2017, the streamflow measured by the gauging station (2.9 to 4.4 mm d⁻¹) is two times lower than the salt streamflow measurement near the outlet (7.5 mm d⁻¹). This difference may be due to a measure bias induced by low flows at the gauging station (see Section 3.3).
- For the series of measurements carried out in September (EPFL), the specific discharge value calculated for the furthest point is abnormally high, and surely due to the underestimation of the upstream area based on the DEM, while in reality this area (not necessarily fitting the surface topography) is more important.

Figure 5. Map of the stream network extent in the Vallon de Nant. C1 and C2 are the two main avalanche couloirs that follow the stream path. The letters a and b identify the different streams options for the along stream gaugings reported in Figure 7. The dashed purple line shows the main stream path after 1 August 2017 storm (until 20 August 2017), based on a satellite images on 2 August 2017 from Planet satellites (Planet, 2017). The Glacier des Martinets extent is based on the Swiss Glacier Inventory 2010 (Fischer et al., 2014).

Figure 6. Result of the 2 dye tracer injections on 30 March 2017 (UTC). The plain lines correspond to the measures of rhodamine B and fluorescein concentrations at the outlet, and the dashed lines to their respective injection time at 2.75 and 1.85 km upstream. In blue is given the streamflow measured at the outlet (mean value of 2.3 mm.d^{-1}) with its 95% confidence interval.

Over the first 3.5 km, the slight streamflow decrease measured in September and November indicates that the main stream is mainly fed by the southern part of the catchment, while in August the more strongly decreasing streamflow shows, in addition to water supplied by southern part, a contribution from the northern slopes of the catchment.

The three series of measurements have a drop in specific discharge around 4 km upstream of the outlet, probably due to river bed infiltration, as observed later in September 2018 (see Section 3.4). Similarly, the streamflow measurements along stream b also show a loss of streamflow (see blue line in Figure 3 top plot), indicating that the water coming from the glacier exfiltrates from the stream to the floodplain area.

Figure 7. Discharge (top) and specific discharge (bottom) along the main stream measured by the Stream Biofilm and Ecosystem Research Laboratory group (EPFL) and the Catchment hydrology group (UNIL). The mean specific discharge measured at the outlet during the measures was 2.2 mm d^{-1} (1.7 to 2.8 mm d^{-1}) on 13 Sept. 2016, 2.0 mm d^{-1} (1.5 to 2.5 mm d^{-1}) on 3 Nov. 2016, and 3.6 mm d^{-1} (2.9 to 4.4 mm d^{-1}) on 9 Aug. 2017. The vertical line at 4.15 km shows the stream network node beyond which the followed path diverges between the main stream (3 Nov. 2016) and an affluent (13 Sept. 2016 and 9 Aug. 2017), noted a and b on the map of the Figure 5.

3.2 Observed streamflow at the outlet

Since September 2016 the gauging station funded jointly by UNIL (IDYST) and the WSL (Forschungsanstalt für Wald, Schnee und Landschaft) measures and sends data of water stage, temperature, conductivity, turbidity, and sediment transport (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Trapezoidal shaped weir at the outlet of the Vallon de Nant. The metallic arm holds the optical height gauge device above the middle point of the weir. Temperature, conductivity, and turbidity probes are located downstream within the 2 metal tubes visible on the left. Sediment transport is measured using geophones located under each metal plate across the weir section.

The water stage is averaged over a minute using an optical height gauge (VEGAPULS WL-61, VEGA, Schiltach, Germany) located above the middle point of a trapezoidal shaped weir. Every minute the temperature and conductivity are measured by a WTW LF 296 probe and a TetraCon 325 probe (Xylem Analytics Germany Sales GmbH & Co, Weilheim, Germany), and the turbidity is measured by a Campbell Scientific OBS300 probe (Campbell Scientific Ltd, Montrouge, France). The conductivity and turbidity data are however unusable as the tubes sheltering the sensors are too frequently clogged by sediments. Sediment transport is measured via a set of geophones, described in detail in the work of Mayoraz (2018), which presents the gauging station in more detail.

An experimental rating curve (Figure 9) has been established from 55 salt streamflow measurements (Ceperley et al., 2018). The standard method was hereby the following: 1 to 5 kg of salt is dissolved in a bucket of stream water, injected from a bridge 120 meters upstream and salinity is measured at the weir using simultaneously 2 salinometers (MADD Easyflow, Madd Technologies Sàrl, Yverdon-les-Bains, Switzerland). A power-relationship is fitted using the nonlinear least squares fitting algorithm of MatLab's "fit" function (MathWorks MatLab 2017a) with the trust region algorithm and least absolute residual method to obtain a 95% confidence interval. The theoretical rating curve associated to a trapezoidal shaped weir is calculated from the Poleni formula (see Appendix 3 - 1).

Figure 9. Rating curve for the Avançon de Nant river at the outlet of the Vallon de Nant, based on 55 salt streamflow measurements. The theoretical rating curve based on the Poleni formula is plot in red.

The Figure 10 shows 5 years of streamflow data estimated thanks to the experimental rating curve. The hydrogram shows a typical snow dominated streamflow regime, with low flow during winter and a high flow period during spring and early summer when the snowpack accumulated during the winter melts. Significant interannual variations can nevertheless be observed, like a dryer year in 2017 (see Table 2) or the occurrence of mid-winter melt in 2018, 2019 and 2020. The presence of peaks (flood events) in summer is due to intense rainfall events, usually associated with summer storms happening during the afternoon or the evening.

The mean annual water temperature measured at the outlet is 5.0 °C, ranging from a frozen river during some days in winter to a mean temperature of 8.5 °C during summer (from 1 July to 31 August 2017).

Figure 10. Five years of streamflow and stream temperature measurement at the outlet of the Vallon de Nant catchment HyS1 (1 January 2016 to 1 January 2021). For a streamflow measured at HyS1, the conversion between $m^3 s^{-1}$ and $mm d^{-1}$ can be done by dividing values by 6.448.

Table 2. General statistics about streamflow data from 2016 to 2020. For each parameter are displayed in parenthesis the inferior and superior values given by the 95% confidence interval on the streamflow estimation. Original data have a 1-minute resolution, so the instant maximum concerns a maximum specific discharge over 1 minute.

Year	Data gaps [%]	Annual total [mm]	Annual mean [mm.d ⁻¹]	Daily min. [mm.d ⁻¹]	Daily max. [mm.d ⁻¹]	Instant max. [mm.d ⁻¹]
2016	11.5	1351 (1105 - 1641)	3.7 (3.0 - 4.5)	0.4 (0.3 - 0.6)	14.4 (12.2 - 16.9)	24.6 (21.2 - 28.4)
2017	6.8	1087 (877 - 1337)	3.0 (2.4 - 3.7)	0.7 (0.5 - 0.9)	15.7 (13.3 - 18.4)	31.5 (27.4 - 36.0)
2018	6.1	1372 (1118 - 1672)	3.8 (3.1 - 4.6)	0.5 (0.4 - 0.7)	14.4 (12.2 - 17.0)	40.8 (35.8 - 46.1)
2019	1.2	1590 (1299 - 1932)	4.4 (3.6 - 5.3)	0.8 (0.6 - 1.1)	19.0 (16.2 - 22.1)	61.3 (54.6 - 68.4)
2020	2.5	1271 (1026 - 1563)	3.5 (2.8 - 4.3)	0.8 (0.6 - 1.0)	11.5 (9.6 - 13.6)	27.6 (23.8 - 31.7)

A quality check of the hydrological data is realized by removing i) erroneous records that are flagged as such by the device recordings and ii) known streamflow disturbance periods due either to gauging station maintenance, frozen stream, or large sediment perturbations. The identification of these disturbance periods is based on water temperature (frozen river) and on pictures taken hourly at the gauging station (see Section 3.3).

3.3 Streamflow uncertainties related to river bed dynamic

Observation via time lapse imagery

A set of cheap sport cameras Xiaomi Yi 1080p (Xiaomi Inc., Beijing, China) were turned into automatic time lapse cameras using an electronic circuit based on an Arduino Nano board (Arduino, 2021) to take a picture every hour during daylight time (see Figure 11).

Figure 11. Adaptation of a cheap sport camera to an automatic time lapse camera for field observations. The camera control buttons are turned into electronic controls by soldering a wire (A); A clock wakes up an Arduino nano board every hour and i) open a relay that power the camera and ii) command the switch on/off and triggering of the camera using logic levels (B); the cameras are enclosed in a waterproof box and attached to a mast, like here at the Glacier weather station (C) and at the gauging station at the outlet (D).

One camera system was set up at the Vallon de Nant outlet to look at the stream, and 3 others at the Auberge, Chalet and Glacier weather stations (see map Figure 20 in Chapter 4) to observe the evolution of visible meteorological events. The cameras set up at the weather stations quickly faced power supply shortages and unidentified issues, so they did not work properly for more than 3 months. Their maintenance has been abandoned due to lack of time.

From September 7th, 2017 to June 11th, 2019, the camera setup at the outlet has taken 5745 images (Figure 12), used for data quality control. It allows to identify or confirm exceptional situations like flood events, frozen stream, accidental streamflow perturbations or instruments maintenance (Figure 12 B, G, F and H).

Figure 12. Pictures of the Avançon de Nant at the outlet taken automatically by a camera, and showing (A) a normal streamflow, (B) a flood event, (C) the stream channelized in the middle of the weir, (D) the streamflow being split into two parts flowing mainly along the sides of the weir, (E) the stream flowing mainly on the left bank of the weir, (F) an exceptional configuration with a rock being deposited right upstream the middle point of the section after a flood event and affecting dramatically the river stage measure, (G) the stream almost completely frozen and (H) some maintenance on the weir.

Long term perturbations are also identified, during low flow ($< 5 \text{ mm.d}^{-1}$) when the stream is i) channelized into one small stream bed in the middle of the weir section, ii) split in two parts flowing on each side of the section, but also iii) during normal streamflow periods (10 to 20 mm.d^{-1} , Figure 13) where the stream is flowing mainly on one side of the weir section (Figure 12 C D and E). These 3 long-term perturbations are problematic as the river stage measure is a point measurement in the middle of the weir, leading to overestimation or underestimation of the stream stage (and thus of the streamflow).

The classification of the pictures (visual appreciation) shows that, over 1.5 years of photographic survey, the stream profile is evenly distributed below the stage level sensor during 30.1 % of the time (Table 3, Figure 13). Configurations with a channelized river in the middle of the weir (overestimation of the streamflow) or divided into two channels flowing on both sides of the weir (underestimation of the streamflow) happen 63.2 % of the time, but only during low flow (observed flow less than 6.0 mm.d^{-1}). A configuration with the stream channel flowing mainly on one side of the weir has been observed only 0.9 % of the time but with a streamflow between 9.8 and 21.0 mm.d^{-1} , showing that uneven water stage does not concern only low flows.

Table 3. Classification of the 5745 pictures taken between September 7th, 2017 and June 11th, 2019 (642 days, 193 days without data) into 7 categories. Periods with more than 24 hours between two consecutive data are consider as periods without data and are not accounted into the total duration.

Stream classification	# of pictures	% of total duration
Normal flow	2034	30.1
Middle flow, 1 channel	1569	26.3
Side flow, 2 channels	1691	36.9
Side flow, 1 channel	62	0.9
Frozen stream	125	2.4
Rock disturbance	204	2.8
Maintenance/experiments	60	0.7

Figure 13. Quality check of the streamflow data using pictures. September 7th, 2017 to June 11th, 2019

It appears that a camera is a precious instrument to critically analyze the data. The used simple camera can only take pictures during daylight and should be upgraded for nighttime imagery, as it misses all events that could happen during nighttime, such as most of flood events linked to strong summer rainfall events usually happening during evenings.

Quantification of river stage measurement bias related to river bed dynamics

An experiment has been realized to evaluate the potential bias caused by a point stage measurement on a channelized river. Three river stage profiles were measured on the field, by hand, using a ruler to estimate the difference between a point measurement in the center point of the weir and an estimate of the river stage distributed on the whole stream profile (Figure 14). It results that in a configuration with the stream being channelized in the middle of the weir, the streamflow could be overestimated by a factor between 1.6 and 1.9. This shows that for such a large weir, the lateral dynamic of the river bed is too important, and a point measurement is not enough to account for these fluctuations; a 2-point or 3-point measurement should be used permanently for a good estimation of the river stage.

Given that the degree of river channelization is evolving continuously, the above estimated factors cannot be used directly to estimate an error estimate but give a first estimation of the possible overestimation in this configuration. In the following, streamflow data are mostly shown as uncorrected measurements without error estimations (for practical reason). Known periods of gauging station maintenance and other obvious erroneous measurements are

shown as missing data. Where appropriate, the order of magnitude of the measurement uncertainty is included in the discussion of results.

Figure 14. Measure (on the left) of 3 stream profiles and (on the right) comparison of streamflow based on i) a point measurement in the middle point of the weir or ii) considering the mean height of the stream profile. The 3 measures are realized (profile #1) on 20/09/2018 at 7:15, (profile #2) on 20/09/2018 at 7:50 and (profile #3) on 10/10/2018 at 14:55 (UTC). Error bars on the streamflow estimation account for the 95% confidence interval from the rating curve, and for the profile integration an additional error due to the manual measure of the stream profile.

3.4 Other sources of streamflow uncertainty

Streamflow blocking by ice / snow jam

Avalanches occur regularly in the Vallon de Nant, especially during the melt season when wet snow avalanches form along the steep slopes along the main stream. It is possible then to count a dozen of avalanches per day, occurring mainly among the steep rocky slopes to the east, and across the steepest grassy slopes on the northwest part of the catchment. The snow packed at the bottom of these slopes creates patches of snow at low elevation that will melt weeks after the surrounding snowpack. This is particularly true for two corridors (C1 and C2 on map Figure 5) where, each year, wet avalanches pack snow up to 5 meters thick and over distances of several hundred meters.

Figure 15. Pictures of a large wet avalanche in the Vallon de Nant on January 31st, 2018 in the avalanche corridor C1 (see map Figure 5), taken (A) from the left bank of the main stream and (B) from the avalanche itself, looking downward in the direction of the main stream.

In 2018, the avalanche in the corridor C1 reached and disturbed the streamflow of the main stream (Figure 15). From field observations, we know that this event occurred between January 11th and January 31st, 2018 probably due to a large snowfall event between January 15 and 17. No further evidence can be provided by the satellite imagery. This avalanche, located around 1.4 km upstream, most likely created a streamflow anomaly on January 22 at 1h25 UTC (Figure 16). Indeed, the streamflow drops for 30 minutes, shows a peak and is then back to normal. Taking the mean streamflow estimation for the 30 minutes before the discharge drop (0.20 and 0.33 m³/s), we estimate that 30 minutes of water accumulation represent 360 to 600 m³ of water. The snow accumulation over the river blocked the water until the pressure being too high and releasing suddenly the reservoir.

Figure 16. Streamflow disturbance on January 22nd, 2018 attributed to a river jam caused by an avalanche. The dark blue curve and light blue envelop correspond to the streamflow and its 95% confidence interval, estimated from the rating curve of the Figure 9.

Modifications of stream channel path after a storm

A storm on 1 August 2017 evening changed the path of the main stream over more than 500 meters and led to a deviation of the stream bed to 100 meters eastward (see Figure 17, Figure 5). After this event, fast erosion processes started creating a new stream channel. However, the river bed was reworked shortly thereafter by the Commune of Bex to put the main stream back in the previous channel and flow under a pedestrian bridge built three weeks before. To date, such stream network changes (and ensuing human intervention) are difficult to trace in this catchment. While this kind of events do not directly influence the observed streamflow at the outlet, they might impact in an unquantifiable way our distributed stream water sampling, water temperature observations as well as piezometric recordings (see Section 3.3).

Figure 17. Pictures showing stream bed modifications after the storm of 1 August 2017, with A) a major deviation of the main stream (see details on map Figure 5) that deviate water from the dry bed visible on the left (with bridge) toward a new channel on the right, and minor deviations of the stream bed forced by a large accumulation of sediments carried by a temporary stream and deviates the main stream over grassy soils.

Subsurface flow

A second dye tracing experiment was completed during an exceptionally dry period, on 20 September 2018 (streamflow at the outlet of 2.8 mm.d^{-1} or $0.44 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$). The amount of recorded rainfall over the preceding week was 2.4 mm, over the preceding three weeks 19.3 mm. On 20 September 2018, the Avançon de Nant main stream was disappearing over 430 m at 4,030 m from the outlet (see map Figure 5). The discharge at the disappearing point was visually estimated to a few liters per minute. A fluorometer was set up 250 m downstream of the resurgence and 14 g of rhodamine injected at the infiltration point. 24 hours later, no signal was measured.

This experiment suggests that either the travel time of infiltrated water through the subsurface ground is very slow or ii) the subsurface travel path during this low flow period led to water export beyond the point of measurement. Even if this experiment does not allow a definite conclusion, streamflow exfiltration to a deeper groundwater system might well be present along the main stream.

Groundwater export

Groundwater export below the gauging station is a common challenge for hydrological studies that rely on streamflow observations at a selected outlet. To date, it is unclear if a part of the streamflow generated within the catchment leaves the catchment as groundwater flow that is not measured at the gauging station. In the work of Thornton et al. (2021a), the decision was made to close the catchment at an outlet downstream for modelling purposes to minimize potential groundwater losses.

Our along stream gauging reveal infiltration in the floodplain area (see Section 3.1), up to potentially a complete disappearance of the stream (discussed above), but there is no evidence that the water infiltrated at this point leaves the catchment, and it is more likely that it will emerge at a short distance downstream.

3.5 Summary

The stream network in the Vallon de Nant is characterized by a dynamic extent, with a permanent stream network flowing all along the year, and tributaries appearing during the snowmelt period and intense rainfall events. Part of the water flowing from the glacier is infiltrating in the floodplain area, which in exceptional situations can lead to a dry stream bed over a few hundred meters.

The exposition of the stream network to extreme events such as avalanches or intense rainfall events can lead to important modifications of its morphology, and a regular monitoring of the stream network is needed for a good understanding of hydrological processes.

We demonstrated the value of a time lapse camera to give a qualitative evaluation of the streamflow measurement at the outlet, demonstrating the need for a river stage measurement accounting for the river bed dynamic, either to have a more accurate measure of the streamflow, or at least to quantify its uncertainty.

A deeper understanding of subsurface flow processes is given through springs and piezometer water temperature monitoring, water conductivity measures and stable isotopes measurements that will be presented and discussed in the Chapter 6.

Appendix 3 – 1: Theoretical streamflow calculation for the gauging station using the Poleni formula applied to a trapezoidal cross-section

The river discharge Q [$m^3 \cdot s^{-1}$] for a rectangular section (Poleni, 1717) can be written as:

$$Q = \frac{2}{3} \mu \bar{b} \sqrt{2g} H^{\frac{3}{2}}, \quad (1)$$

where μ is a factor that accounts for the overfall shape [-], we take $\mu = 0,55$ as a typical value recommended for check dams; \bar{b} the mean equivalent section width [m], g the acceleration due to the gravity ($g = 9.81 m \cdot s^{-2}$) and H the total head [m].

Due to the particular geometry of the weir, with border slopes of 45° , the mean width equals:

$$\bar{b} = b + y_c, \quad (2)$$

with b the weir width at the base, $b = 5,3 m$ in our case.

Like the water height is measured at the critical point (Figure 18), the dimensionless Froude number Fr expressing the ratio between kinetic and potential energy is equal to 1:

$$Fr = \frac{v_c}{\sqrt{gy_c}} = 1, \quad (3)$$

with v_c the critical velocity [$m \cdot s^{-1}$] and y_c the critical water height [m].

Figure 18. Conservation of the total head H over a weir (Böll, 1997).

So, we deduce from (3) the critical velocity:

$$v_c = \sqrt{gy_c} \quad (4)$$

The Bernoulli theorem of conservation of energy (total head) along a streamline of flowing fluid gives:

$$H = y_c + \frac{v_c^2}{2g} \quad (5)$$

Using (4) and (5):

$$H = y_c + \frac{gy_c}{2g} \quad (6)$$

$$\leftrightarrow H = \frac{3}{2}y_c \quad (7)$$

Thanks to the total head expression (3) and the equivalent section width equation (2), we express the initial formula (1) as:

$$Q = \frac{2}{3}\mu(b + y_c)\sqrt{2g}\left(\frac{3}{2}y_c\right)^{\frac{3}{2}} \quad (8)$$

$$\leftrightarrow Q = \frac{2}{3}\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^{\frac{3}{2}}\mu\sqrt{2g}(b + y_c)(y_c)^{\frac{3}{2}} \quad (9)$$

$$\leftrightarrow Q = \mu\sqrt{3gy_c}(b + y_c)y_c \quad (10)$$